

D4.1 – Activity Plan for User Interaction

Lead Partner:	CNRS
Version:	v00
Author(s) (Name, Organisation):	Federica Tanlongo (EPOS ERIC), Karin Sigloch (CNRS)
Contributors (Name, Organisation)	Lucia Luzi (INGV / EPOS ERIC), Jan Michalek (UiB), Rossana Paciello (INGV / EPOS ERIC)
Status:	Submitted
Dissemination Level:	PU

Deliverable Abstract

This document describes the EPOS ON action plan to expand and diversify its user community through user interaction. EPOS ON will accelerate the implementation of EPOS' broader strategy by improving the user experience of the EPOS Platform, building capacity through specific training, and boosting communication.

A key component of the strategy is engaging early-career researchers through specialized training, involvement in EPOS development, and travel grants.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the EPOS ON Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The EPOS ON project is funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under grant n° 101131592.

QUALITY CONTROL

Date	Name	Organisation
Reviewer 1:	Anna Leśnodorska	Instytut Geofizyki Polskiej Akademii Nauk
Reviewer 2:	Ronald Pijnenburg	Utrecht University

TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
DDSS	Data, Data Products, Software and Services: the body of research outputs made available through the EPOS platform
DEI	Diversity, Equality and Inclusion
DOA	Description of Action
ECR	Early Career Researchers
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ICS	Integrated Core Services, provides the core of the EPOS e-infrastructure ensuring interoperability between the data and services provided by TCS
ICS-TCS interaction	the collaborative framework that ensures the communication between the integration (ICS) and community (TCS) layers within EPOS
Long Tail of Science	In science terms, the long tail is made up of the funded projects handled by individual laboratories or small groups of researchers, as opposed to large, expensive collaborations.
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCC	Services Coordination Committee, fosters harmonization of data and metadata standards across TCS

TCS	Thematic Core Services, i.e. the thematic communities that harmonise and aggregate data and scientific products in a specific Solid Earth discipline (e.g. Seismology, GNSS, Volcanology...) and provide them through services in the EPOS Delivery framework
WP	Work Package
UX	User Experience

Table of Contents

1	<i>Executive summary</i>	6
2	<i>Introduction: the EPOS user strategy</i>	7
2.1	Context and rationale	7
2.2	Target, objectives and methodology	8
2.3	The EPOS user strategy	9
2.4	Value proposition	10
3	<i>EPOS Platform - improve user experience, build capacity</i>	12
3.1	Step 1: Systematic collection of user requirements and feedback	12
3.2	Step 2: Identifying and addressing usage roadblocks	12
3.3	Step 3: Developing a roadmap for user experience enhancements	13
3.4	Improving user experience and promoting engagement through training	13
4	<i>Communication and community building</i>	15
4.1	Expanding the user base through targeted communication strategies	15
4.2	Enhancing interaction and knowledge exchange	16
4.3	Harmonizing vocabulary for clear and consistent communication	16
5	<i>Engaging early-career researchers</i>	17
5.1	Select: identify and showcase promising use cases by ECRs and select ambassadors among them	17
5.2	Train: organise specialized summer schools and training events to accelerate ECR's proficiency with the EPOS Platform.....	17
5.2.1	EPOS Summer schools.....	18
5.3	Engage: involve active ECRs in improving EPOS, its functionalities, and in exploring new use cases.	18
5.4	Reward: support ECRs presenting their EPOS-based research at international conferences and events through the EPOS GO! travel grant program.	19
5.4.1	EPOS GO!.....	19
5.5	Optimising the strategy: interviews and feedback collection	20
5.5.1	Swapping notes with other initiatives.....	20
7	<i>KPIs</i>	21
8	<i>Conclusions</i>	23
9	<i>References</i>	24

10 APPENDIX I - EPOS Summer School concept and target.....25

10.1 Concept 25

10.2 Ideal target audience 25

10.3 DEI Statement..... 26

1 Executive summary

This document outlines the **EPOS ON action plan** to expand and diversify its user community through enhanced user interaction.

The EPOS user strategy is built on four pillars: **attracting new users** through targeted communication, **training users** to become proficient with the EPOS Platform, **collecting feedback** to continuously improve the platform, and **rewarding and retaining users** through incentives and recognition.

EPOS ON will accelerate the implementation of this strategy by focusing on three key areas: improving the **user experience** of the EPOS Platform, **building capacity** through specialized training programs, and **boosting communication** to engage a broader audience.

A central component of this strategy is the engagement of **early-career researchers (ECRs)** as early adopters, through tailored training opportunities, and active involvement in the development of EPOS services. We will facilitate their visibility, peer recognition and support, e.g., via **travel grants** to present EPOS-based research at international conferences and to train other users.

The EPOS user strategy represents a proactive and user-centric approach to maximizing the platform's impact and ensuring its long-term sustainability. By fostering a strong and active user community, EPOS will continue to advance research and innovation in solid Earth science.

2 Introduction: the EPOS user strategy

2.1 Context and rationale

A robust, regular and engaged user community is crucial for the success of any research infrastructure. Since EPOS entered its operational phase, cultivating a strong and skilled user base has been essential to ensure the infrastructure's alignment with researchers' needs, its continued scientific relevance, its adoption of emerging technologies, and its sustained growth.

Since its inception, EPOS has transformed solid Earth science by unifying diverse communities and overcoming inconsistencies in standards, vocabularies, and data sharing approaches. Its Thematic Core Services (TCS), each representing a sub-community with solid-earth sciences (Seismology, Geodesy, Volcanology, Geology,...) have successfully established a harmonized, FAIR-compliant data infrastructure, broadening engagement with scientific communities and stakeholders.

At the heart of the EPOS research infrastructure, the EPOS Platform provides access to data and products from around 300 scientific data services across Europe. The EPOS Platform is a valuable resource for anyone who needs access to high-quality earth science data and provides open access to a comprehensive collection of data and products from a variety of sources. The portal was publicly launched in April 2023 and since then is gaining visibility and new users (Fig. 1). While individual TCS typically have established user communities of their intra-disciplinary data services, such a user community largely remains to be established for the cross-disciplinary data offerings of the EPOS Platform that spans across all 10 TCS and across EPOS' member countries.

Visits Over Time

Fig 1. - The graph shows the number of monthly visits to the EPOS Platform, which have increased since its public launch in April 2023.

2.2 Target, objectives and methodology

The grand challenge of the EPOS user strategy is to position the EPOS Platform as a fundamental tool that researchers integrate into their daily work because they are fully aware of its capabilities and cross-disciplinary scope, which is globally unique.

EPOS is a bottom-up research infrastructure (RI), and its initial phase of community building was inherent to the process of developing the infrastructure and its services. Before entering the operational phase, user engagement coincided with collaboration within the community who were building the infrastructure and its services. Since the platform's public launch in 2023, the engagement of new users has largely relied on the thematic communities' existing networks and their capacity to disseminate information through scientific publications and presentations at major events. However, with the transition to the operational phase, there is a need to accelerate efforts to connect with the full range of potential users, which is much larger than EPOS' original developer community. We need to implement targeted communication strategies that enhance the platform's visibility and demonstrate its value to a broader audience. By doing so, EPOS aims to expand its user base, ensuring the cross-disciplinary platform is widely adopted as a vital resource for the global solid Earth science community, in addition to any more specialized data offerings by individual TCS communities. The portal's new offerings reflect and accompany the increasingly cross-disciplinary nature of research in geosciences.

The main target user group of the EPOS Platform are solid-earth geoscientists. The services are universally open, so that other stakeholders can also benefit from the platform. Secondary target users include civil servants, industry and education.

A key strategic objective of EPOS ON is to **expand and diversify the user community**, fostering a wider, more engaged, and multidisciplinary user base for EPOS data and services. This implies strengthening EPOS' outreach action and targeting potential users beyond EPOS' established community, addressing in particular the long tail of science. We place significant emphasis on promoting the usage of the EPOS Platform since the earliest career stages (by students and ECRs) because this group carries out much of the hands-on research, are often working on more cross-disciplinary projects, are well-placed to acquire new technical skills and tools, and are likely to carry those forward through their careers and to their future students. To maximize the research infrastructure's impact, Work Package 4 (WP4) of EPOS ON focuses on optimizing user engagement, coordinating with all technical work packages to achieve the sub-objectives.

The methodological approach of WP4 includes four steps:

1. identifying weaknesses in the existing EPOS' User Strategy and defining measures to strengthen it;
2. leveraging training programs as a means of engaging with new users and ensuring capacity building within the community;
3. Continuous improvement of the usability/intuitiveness of the EPOS Platform, by bi-annual cycles of
 - a. user testing (both blind, i.e. no instructions provided, and scenario-steered),
 - b. user feedback collection,
 - c. feedback analysis by a designated group within WP4 in the framework of ICS-TCS interaction activities., This group will advise the development team on further improvement of the user interface
 - d. engaging with TCSs representatives to work on feedback regarding possible improvements of the services provided by TCSs communities
4. Developing the next generation of EPOS data users and providers through engagement with early-career researchers.

Aligned with the EPOS 2024–2028 strategy, as well as EPOS' operational communication plan, WP4 directly supports the strategic goals of fostering infrastructure usage and broadening the EPOS community. By addressing the needs of researchers, data providers, industry stakeholders, policymakers, and international partners, WP4 contributes to the long-term sustainability and impact of EPOS as a global research infrastructure for the solid-earth sciences.

2.3 The EPOS user strategy

The EPOS user strategy is built around four key pillars: **Attract, Train, Improve through feedback, and Reward & Retain.**

1. **Attract:** Increase the visibility of the EPOS Platform and expand the user base through targeted scientific dissemination, participation in key events, and networking activities.
2. **Train:** Transform newcomers and basic users into advanced users through comprehensive training programs, including online training programmes, seminars, summer schools, and peer-learning initiatives, such as for example Communities of Practice.
3. **Collect Feedback & Improve:** Foster a culture of continuous improvement by engaging users in providing feedback and suggesting new features. This includes focus groups (e.g., user experience improvement groups), feedback forms, analytics on platform usage, and establishing two-way communication channels online and in person (e.g., through summer schools, training sessions).
4. **Reward & Retain:** Incentivize continued usage and highlight exemplary and innovative applications of the EPOS Platform through prizes, travel grants, and enhanced visibility via dissemination support, events, and publication assistance.

This strategy aims to create a dynamic, user-centered research infrastructure that evolves in response to the needs of the geoscience community.

2.4 Value proposition

Key to engaging a wide and committed user community is the capacity to provide added value to users and to present it in a clear, consistent and appealing way.

The EPOS Platform is an essential tool for researchers and other professionals seeking high-quality, multidisciplinary Earth science data. It offers universal, synoptic, and open access to a vast array of datasets and data products from over 500 authoritative scientific data and service providers across Europe, integrating quality-vetted data from different disciplinary fields such as seismology, volcanology, and geodesy.

The portal's user-friendly interface simplifies the search and retrieval process, while advanced visualization tools, including extended time-series plotting, enable cross-disciplinary and in-depth analysis of complex earth processes.

By adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, the EPOS Platform ensures that all data are reliable and standardized. EPOS fosters collaboration among researchers by providing a common platform for sharing data and products.

Benefits of using the EPOS Platform:

- Access to a wide range of data and products:** Open and synoptic access to a vast number of authoritative datasets and scientific products from hundreds of European data and service providers across solid-earth disciplines.
- Improved data quality:** The EPOS Platform ensures that all data and products meet international standards.
- Easier data discoverability and access:** The EPOS Platform provides a user-friendly interface that makes it easy to search, discover and access data.
- Increased collaboration:** The EPOS Platform fosters collaboration among researchers by providing a common platform for sharing data and products

3 EPOS Platform - improve user experience, build capacity

Growing the user base of the EPOS Platform and establishing it as a highly useful working tool is central to EPOS' success. This is a continuous process, requiring ongoing efforts to align the infrastructure with evolving research needs and technological advancements.

To this end, EPOS ON will **improve the user experience** of the EPOS Platform through a positive feedback loop that implements and improves features based on constant user feedback. In EPOS ON WP4, we will advance through three steps: (1) collection of structured feedback from users; (2) identification and analysis of existing roadblocks to platform usage; and (3) definition of a roadmap with recommendations to improve the platform based on steps (1) and (2).

To this end, a dedicated group involving researchers and data practitioners, with at least one representative designated by each TCS, will be created. Special attention will be dedicated to include in the group researchers in different career stages and from different countries, in order to consider different viewpoints.

3.1 Step 1: Systematic collection of user requirements and feedback

A robust mechanism will be established to gather structured insights from users regarding their experience with the EPOS Platform, as well as their needs and expectations for its evolution. This action will include:

- **Analysis of usage statistics** to better understand the users' behaviour on the platform, to identify potential problems as well as favourite features.
- **Usability and user experience (UX) testing** to identify areas for improvement and potential additions.
- **User consultations**, including surveys, interviews and focus groups to understand the researchers' needs for new services, features, and datasets. Qualitative and quantitative, structured information will be integrated in order to obtain a comprehensive picture of usage patterns and perceptions. Findings from the points above will be discussed by dedicated EPOS bodies (SCC, IT Board), prioritized and then transferred to the internal EPOS issue tracker to be shared with the developers' team for taking appropriate actions to improve the EPOS Platform.

3.2 Step 2: Identifying and addressing usage roadblocks

User feedback will drive a comprehensive analysis to identify barriers hindering the adoption of the EPOS Platform and define, prioritise and implement possible solutions. Common challenges may include

- **Technical barriers**, such as navigation difficulties, interoperability issues, or lack of certain datasets.
- **Non-technical barriers**, including limited visibility, lack of training materials, or ineffective communication.

Overcoming these roadblocks will require coordinated efforts from multiple EPOS stakeholders, ensuring that both technical and non-technical solutions are efficiently and effectively executed.

3.3 Step 3: Developing a roadmap for user experience enhancements

Findings from the first two steps will inform the creation of a strategic roadmap, which will provide recommendations for:

- Improving platform accessibility and ease of use.
- Enhancing the discoverability of relevant data and services.
- Streamlining the onboarding process for new users.
- Strengthening communication channels to improve user support and engagement.

3.4 Improving user experience and promoting engagement through training

Training is a fundamental aspect of this strategy, ensuring that researchers, as well as secondary audiences, feel confident and at ease in using the EPOS Platform and can leverage its full potential. For the initial purposes of this plan, we can identify two broad categories of training needs:

- 1) training needs related to knowledge and skills related to Open Science, FAIR, and RDM in the specific context of the geosciences and EPOS in particular. This refers not only to researchers using the EPOS platform, who are the primary target of the user engagement strategy, but also to other targets including students and data providers who contribute data and scientific products to EPOS.
- 2) training needs connected to lowering the access barriers to EPOS Platform adoption. This specifically addresses new and prospective users, and is a synergistic action with the activities aimed at improving the overall UX for portal users.

While the first category of training needs is not expected to vary significantly throughout the project, it is reasonable that this second one will dwindle (but not disappear altogether) as UX improves.

In close collaboration with thematic communities through the EPOS Service Coordination Committee, EPOS ON will focus on:

- **Collecting and analyzing training needs**, also based on the roadblock analysis discussed above. This will be based on surveys/interviews both online and in person (with the latter mainly piggybacking events organised in the framework of EPOS ON or where an EPOS ON presence is foreseen. e.g. the EPOS Days, EGU etc).
- **Co-designing learning paths** with TCSs for researchers, as well as for secondary audiences such as civil servants, industry professionals, and citizen scientists.
- **Developing tailored training materials** for diverse audiences and expertise levels.
- **Elaborating use cases**, tailored by thematic areas and by user type, in collaboration with TCS communities.

- **Building a network of educators** across EPOS countries to foster knowledge sharing, building on Train-the-trainers schemes and providing pedagogical, communication and facilitation tips to improve the quality of the training outcomes
- **Creating FAIR-by-design training resources**, with rich metadata for easy discovery and complementary materials (e.g. training facilitators guidelines, customisable exercises and activities etc) to facilitate reuse. This will also include actions to facilitate the creation and provision of materials by senior trainers/university professors in the community, and to explore additional funding opportunities outside EPOS ON to support this outcome (e.g. with dedicated grants).
- **Establishing a training hub** to support trainers, trainees, and community interaction and facilitate peer learning, knowledge exchange, and cross-disciplinary collaboration.
- **Exploring opportunities to include EPOS-related courses/training in Academia**, e.g. through “visiting” courses or the introduction of the EPOS Platform in university teaching programmes.

By integrating these elements into a cohesive action plan, EPOS will strengthen user engagement, ensuring a more accessible and widely adopted research infrastructure with lasting impact on the solid Earth science community.

4 Communication and community building

Effective communication and community engagement are crucial to broadening the EPOS user base and fostering a dynamic and collaborative research environment. EPOS ON will implement a multi-faceted strategy that enhances outreach, interaction, and knowledge exchange while ensuring consistency in communication across the EPOS Research Infrastructure.

4.1 Expanding the user base through targeted communication strategies

EPOS ON will develop new communication approaches to attract a broader audience, including early-career researchers, interdisciplinary scientists, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. These efforts will include:

- **Tailored messaging** that highlights the value of EPOS data and services for different user groups to better connect with them by aligning to their needs and expectations. One of the EPOS ON goals is to extend outreach beyond traditional EPOS communities, not only by reaching other thematic groups but also by engaging new stakeholders, such as civil servants and certain private sector actors. As we start with limited knowledge of these target groups we will need to adopt an adaptive, exploratory approach. On a smaller scale, message customization will also be beneficial within the research community itself—for example, differentiating communication for senior researchers versus students, or for seismologists versus ground instability experts, etc.
- **Showcasing impactful research and user experiences** through compelling **storytelling techniques** across multiple formats, such as feature articles, videos, podcasts, and social media campaigns. The aim is to make success stories more visible, relatable, and inspiring for potential users. Typical stories to be selected will ideally exemplify different types of impact, e.g. on science advances, society (e.g. risk reduction), or education.
- **Facilitating the adoption of automated workflows to improve productivity** in data handling, lowering the technical barriers through dedicated training and the provision of sample code (e.g. Jupyter notebook) and documentation.
- **Encouraging citations and visibility** by providing standardized text for users to acknowledge EPOS and the relevant DDSS discovered and used through the EPOS Platform in their publications and a simple process to inform the communication team of their outputs.
- **Focusing on high-level scientific communication** in peer-reviewed journals and at relevant scientific events to involve senior researchers and raise their awareness on the potential benefits of the EPOS Platform in multi- and interdisciplinary research. We will actively identify and leverage opportunities to engage with their users in their own communities, including forums, conferences, and dedicated events.
- **Recognizing and rewarding engagement** by featuring outstanding use cases in EPOS communication channels, inviting researchers to present at events, and offering incentives such as travel grants for innovative applications of the EPOS Platform. Participation incentives can be complemented by intermediate micro-rewards—such as merchandise, exclusive chats with experts, etc—offered more frequently and enhancing our presence and

visibility throughout the year, ensuring broader and more sustained engagement by reaching a wider audience.

4.2 Enhancing interaction and knowledge exchange

EPOS ON will strengthen communication channels and introduce new tools that encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing. Key actions include:

- **Exploring the opportunity to establish a community of practice** for trained users to keep them engaged through continuous updates, expert Q&As, and knowledge-sharing activities.
- **Facilitating two-way communication** by actively soliciting feedback on training programs and the EPOS Platform, using insights to refine and improve services.
- **Providing interactive communication tools**, such as forums, chat platforms, or AI-driven assistants, to support peer learning, facilitate data discovery, and recommend relevant datasets based on user research interests.
- **Implementing a push notification system** to keep users informed about platform enhancements, new datasets, and key updates. Additionally, users who provide feedback or report issues will be notified about the actions taken in response to their input.

4.3 Harmonizing vocabulary for clear and consistent communication

We will improve communication effectiveness across the EPOS Research Infrastructure by harmonizing terminology and standardizing the language used across services and documentation. This will include:

- **Developing a shared vocabulary** to ensure clarity and consistency in user guidance and training materials.
- **Aligning terminology across thematic communities (TCSs)** to facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration and reduce barriers to understanding.
- **Ensuring the availability of multilingual documentation** where relevant, also in collaboration with EPOS' national nodes, initiatives and consortia, to support the diverse research community of Europe and beyond.

Thus, EPOS ON will create a more inclusive, interactive, and engaged user community that can fully leverage the data and service offerings of EPOS.

5 Engaging early-career researchers

EPOS prioritizes engaging early-career researchers (ECRs) to further a sustained, cutting-edge and dynamic research ecosystem.

ECRs are in the formative stages of developing their research methodologies, making them more receptive to incorporating new tools and workflows, such as those provided by EPOS.

Research projects are more cross-disciplinary than ever, and ECRs are at the forefront by virtue of doing much of the hands-on work in science. They may benefit most from the enhanced data discoverability, accessibility, and openness facilitated by EPOS's open science approach, as they usually still lack the extensive word-of-mouth networks that help senior researchers to discover exciting data and research topics.

ECRs are at a pivotal point in building their professional networks. EPOS-facilitated events can hence catalyze connections that will foster future interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. Today's ECRs will shape the future of geoscience: by embedding EPOS within their research practices, we can secure its role as an integral part of the scientific landscape for the next generation.

The EPOS ON engagement strategy for ECRs follows the four-step approach designed for the general user strategy, with a slight change in the inception phase: **Select, Train, Engage, and Reward**.

5.1 **Select:** identify and showcase promising use cases by ECRs and select ambassadors among them

In the selection phase, we identify promising ECR contributions that can effectively showcase the range of uses for the EPOS Platform and of the resources available through it. This includes highlighting impactful use cases, innovative research outputs, and scientific publications that demonstrate how EPOS data, services, and tools can advance geoscientific knowledge. Selection criteria are designed to be inclusive across user demographics, countries and TCS communities. Through open calls, competitions, and targeted outreach, EPOS ON aims to discover emerging talent and amplify their work within the broader scientific community.

Selected contributions will be disseminated through strategic communication channels, including scientific conferences, workshops, and digital platforms, where storytelling techniques are employed to inspire and engage further platform users.

5.2 **Train:** organise specialized summer schools and training events to accelerate ECR's proficiency with the EPOS Platform

Training is at the core of the EPOS ON strategy. It empowers ECRs with the skills and knowledge to maximize the potential of EPOS services. Practice-oriented, tailored training activities will provide ECRs with direct experience in accessing, analyzing, and integrating EPOS data into their research workflows. Flagship initiatives like the **EPOS Summer Schools** will offer intensive, immersive

learning environments where participants engage with real-world case studies, collaborative projects, and expert-led sessions.

EPOS ON will also organise specialized workshops, webinars, and training events tailored to different scientific domains and technical competencies. These activities will build technical proficiency and promote a culture of open science, data interoperability, and multidisciplinary collaboration – equipping ECRs with essential skills for modern geoscience research.

Throughout the EPOS ON project, we will offer a variety of training opportunities dedicated to ECRs, both in-person and online. These include:

- Two EPOS summer schools.
- Dedicated sessions during the EPOS Days.
- A workshop connecting ECRs and industry professionals in the cutting-edge field of high-enthalpy geothermal energy, organized in collaboration with Task 2.2 within the Krafla Magma Testbeds initiative.
- Training sessions showcasing EPOS offerings at thematic community (TCS) meetings or other relevant events (e.g. EGU, workshops of major geoscience initiatives).

5.2.1 EPOS Summer schools

EPOS Summer Schools are designed to offer practical training on cross-disciplinary research data in the geosciences. We will focus the training on discovering and processing multidisciplinary data in the EPOS Platform. Participants will learn to design open-science data management and sharing workflows, including data discovery, processing, and Jupyter Notebook use. The program will cover research data management, from foundational concepts to complex topics like legislation, licensing, and persistent identifiers.

We will adopt a pragmatic, hands-on approach that emphasizes skills that will be immediately applicable. Sessions and group work allow participants to apply their knowledge to real-world use cases, including some they bring themselves. Interactive sessions will foster discussion on the challenges and benefits of open science and FAIR data, addressing common misconceptions. Recognizing participants' diverse backgrounds and ICT skills, participant groups will bring together users with complementary expertise, which promotes collaboration and teamwork.

The first EPOS Summer School, scheduled for June 2025, will pilot this concept. For detailed information on the curriculum and structure, see **Appendix I**.

5.3 Engage: involve active ECRs in improving EPOS, its functionalities, and in exploring new use cases.

Beyond training, EPOS ON will actively involve ECRs in the co-development of new features and the enhancement of existing services, fostering a sense of ownership and contribution to the research infrastructure. Engagement opportunities are designed to encourage active participation in shaping the EPOS Platform and tools. ECRs are invited to contribute feedback on service usability and

collaborate on the development of new use cases that address emerging scientific challenges, also in collaboration with WP2 and WP3.

EPOS ON also facilitates networking opportunities through scientific events, where ECRs can connect with peers, mentors, and senior researchers across disciplines. By creating these spaces for dialogue and collaboration, EPOS helps ECRs build lasting professional relationships and gain visibility within the geoscientific community. This active engagement not only enriches EPOS services with fresh perspectives but also strengthens the integration of EPOS into the daily research practices of users that will go on to be experienced scientists with research groups of their own, a concept for anchoring and multiplying EPOS' user base in the long run.

5.4 Reward: support ECRs presenting their EPOS-based research at international conferences and events through the EPOS GO! travel grant program.

Recognizing and rewarding outstanding contributions is a key motivator for sustained ECR engagement. The **EPOS GO!** travel grant program exemplifies this approach by supporting ECRs who have produced quality research using EPOS data and services. These grants will enable recipients to present their work at prestigious international conferences and scientific events, providing valuable exposure and opportunities to network with leading experts in their fields. In addition to travel grants, EPOS highlights ECR achievements through featured stories, interviews, and showcases on its communication platforms. Celebrating these individual accomplishments serves to inspire other future users to engage with EPOS resources. By acknowledging and rewarding excellence, EPOS reinforces the value of ECR contributions to the broader scientific ecosystem and supports their professional development.

5.4.1 EPOS GO!

The EPOS GO! travel grant program is designed to support ECRs presenting research using the EPOS Platform at international conferences and events. ECRs with scientific use cases leveraging EPOS to address research questions, ideally inter- or trans-disciplinary, will be eligible. Applicants will submit an abstract to a European scientific event (conference, forum, etc.), having prepared a related paper. Proper acknowledgment of the EPOS Platform and relevant datasets, services, and products used in the research per the EPOS DDSS Citation Guide¹, will be required. Upon abstract acceptance, ECRs can apply for a grant covering travel and accommodation. Travel grants for summer schools and other events may also be awarded based on CV, motivation, and research projects, including direct appointments by thematic communities.

¹https://www.epos-eu.org/sites/default/files/2024-03/01_EPOS%20DDSS%20Citation%20Guide%20v3.0_11Mar2024_270324_BA.pdf

5.5 Optimising the strategy: interviews and feedback collection

Through these integrated initiatives, EPOS will support the current generation of ECRs and cultivate a vibrant, engaged community of researchers for whom EPOS tools and open science practices are integral to their work. This long-term investment in ECR engagement ensures that EPOS will continue to evolve in response to the needs of the scientific community, driven by the curiosity, innovation, and collaborative spirit of early-career researchers. WP4 team will conduct, early in the project lifetime, in-depth interviews in order to fine-tune the strategy to the ECR's real needs and expectations. Throughout the implementation phase, additional extensive feedback will be gathered from the ECR participating in the various engagement initiatives that will be analysed and used to further improve the work plan.

5.5.1 Swapping notes with other initiatives

In order to complement the feedback collection, we will engage with relevant UX and user engagement initiatives, particularly within Research Infrastructures and Virtual Research Environments. A key collaboration is with **AuScope**, EPOS' Australian counterpart, which has conducted in-depth studies on RI user profiles, objectives, and interactions with data and services. These insights are crucial for improving user experience. However, as user needs evolve, Research Infrastructures must maintain continuous, two-way engagement to gather feedback, anticipate future requirements, and ensure a user-centric approach.

7 KPIs

Progress in implementing the EPOS user strategy will be monitored through key outputs for each activity and a set of quantitative indicators. These indicators serve both to enhance activities and to report outcomes to EPOS ERIC bodies and external reviewers. The collected data will include in particular participation in events and training, production and reuse of materials, and qualitative insights from user feedback and training satisfaction surveys.

The initial success thresholds are indicated in the table below. These may be revised in time during the project to aim for more ambitious objectives.

User engagement and training KPIs and success thresholds		
KPI	Success threshold	Measurement
FAIR-by-design training materials delivered during the project	8 for at least 2 different targets	n° of slidesets and/ or with trainers' guide published with rich metadata and DOI
Scientific use cases for training and education purposes	10 (at least one per TCS)	document describing UC published
Sample Jupyter notebook code delivered	10 (at least one per TCS)	sample code made available on github
Summer schools organised	2	EPOS ON summer school organised
Summer schools participants	40	participants to a EPOS ON summer school
Engaged ECR through dedicated actions	40/year	Number of unique ECR engaged through dedicated actions (training, EPOS GO! etc)
Training events organised	8	online and onsite training organised during the project lifetime
Training participants	500	n° of participants to online and onsite training

Training time delivered throughout the project	6.000 hours	person-hours (live and self-paced)
Frequency of user feedback/UX tests	twice a year	feedback collection activities through surveys, interviews or usability tests.
Average training Feedback score	8/10 or more	Average score of trainees satisfaction as expressed in the training feedback form
Average usability feedback score	8/10 or more by the end of the project	Average score of user satisfaction related to UX as expressed in feedback forms
% increase of visits to the EPOS Platform	15% /year	Increase in visits compared to the status at the beginning of the project, expressed in percentage

In addition to these project-related indicators, as a part of its institutional activity, EPOS ERIC annually monitors general and specific KPIs to assess the performance in key areas of activity and act on the basis of the results. This includes general KPIs and specific metrics for the assessment of the EPOS Operational Communication Plan².

² <https://zenodo.org/records/14860590>

8 Conclusions

The **EPOS ON action plan** is designed to complement, reinforce and accelerate **EPOS' broader user strategy**, which provides the foundation for engaging, supporting, and expanding the research community using the EPOS infrastructure. The **EPOS user strategy** focuses on attracting new users, training them to become proficient, gathering feedback for continuous improvement, and fostering long-term engagement. **EPOS ON accelerates these efforts** through targeted actions designed to improve user experience, build capacity through training, and boost communication with the different target users.

In EPOS ON, we focus on **optimising the user experience** by systematically collecting feedback, identifying and addressing usability barriers, and implementing platform improvements that align with evolving research needs. The project also strengthens **training and capacity building**, with a particular emphasis on **early-career researchers (ECRs)**, who are at a pivotal stage in shaping their professional experience, and with it the future of geosciences research. Through dedicated summer schools, workshops, and the **EPOS GO! travel grant program**, EPOS ON provides ECRs with the skills, resources, and opportunities to fully integrate EPOS services into their research workflows.

With this action plan we will also **enhance communication and community-building efforts** to extend the reach of EPOS well beyond its existing user base. By improving visibility, fostering interdisciplinary knowledge exchange, and harmonising scientific vocabulary across thematic communities, the project strengthens collaboration and ensures that EPOS remains an indispensable tool for solid Earth science research.

These complementary actions **will reinforce and accelerate EPOS' long-term strategy, ensuring a dynamic, engaged, and growing user community** that will continue to benefit from EPOS data and services, while also supporting the Research Infrastructure's evolution in response to the needs of the geoscience community.

9 References

Reference n°	Reference
[R1] EPOS Operational Communication Plan	https://zenodo.org/records/14780737

10 APPENDIX I - EPOS Summer School concept and target

10.1 Concept

The first EPOS ON Summer School will focus on research data in the geosciences and its practical applications. The program offers a comprehensive exploration of Research Data Management in the context of GeoSciences, starting with foundational concepts and progressing to essential yet often challenging topics such as legislation, licensing, and persistent identifiers.

A key highlight will be using and processing multidisciplinary data, particularly within the EPOS Platform. Participants will learn to design workflows for managing and sharing data in an open-science environment, including data discovery, processing, and leveraging Jupyter Notebook technology.

With a pragmatic approach, the school aims to equip participants with actionable knowledge and skills they can immediately apply to their research. Ample space in the agenda will be dedicated to hands-on sessions and group work, allowing participants to test their skills using real-world use cases, including a selection of those presented by themselves.

The program will also provide space for reflection and group discussions, addressing challenges and benefits of open science and FAIR data and demystifying common misconceptions. Recognizing the diverse backgrounds and ICT proficiency of participants as an added value for the school, groups will be thoughtfully organized to combine complementary skills, fostering collaboration and enhancing real-world teamwork capabilities.

10.2 Ideal target audience

The EPOS ON Summer School is an intensive program designed for Ph.D. students, candidates, and postdocs from different scientific communities, whose daily research work builds upon multidisciplinary data.

- PHD students and candidates, Postdocs, Early Career Scientists
- From all TCS/scientific communities,
- Open to new communities (e.g. Built Environment, Gravimetry, GeoThermal energy...)
- Working with solid earth data, preferably different types of data. Basics of computer programming would be an advantage
- Having an inter- or trans-disciplinary Use Case /Scientific question
 - Use cases don't necessarily have to be complete, as one of the objectives of the school is to help develop (some of) the participants' Use Cases.

Target participation: 15-20 participants, 1 per TCS + possibly 2-4 from new communities (e.g. gravimetry, geothermal, built environment, etc), 1-2 each from EarthScope and AuScope and some

10.3 DEI Statement

EPOS is firmly dedicated to advancing diversity, equality and inclusion in every training opportunity we offer. We invite registrations from individuals of diverse ethnicities, cultural and religious backgrounds, genders, sexual orientations, and at all stages of their careers.